

Lanczos Spintensor via the Andersson-Edgar's Generator

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Abstract:

For arbitrary geometries with Petrov types O, N, III, and D (empty), we construct the Andersson-Edgar's generator for the Lanczos spinor.

Keywords: *Andersson-Edgar's potential, Conformal tensor, Newman-Penrose formalism, 2-spinors, Canonical null tetrad, Petrov classification, Lanczos potential, Gödel spacetime.*

Introduction

In López-Bonilla et al. (1993) was obtained the Lanczos generator for any empty spacetime of Petrov type D, with the following Newman-Penrose (NP) components (Lanzos, 1962a; Lanzos, 1962b; Perjés, 2006):

$$\Omega_2 = \pi \psi_2^{-\frac{2}{3}}, \quad \Omega_6 = \mu \psi_2^{-\frac{2}{3}}, \quad \Omega_r = 0, \quad r \neq 2, 6, \quad (1)$$

in terms of the spin coefficients (Stephani et al., 2003; Newman, & Penrose, 2009) associated to the canonical null tetrad (López-Bonilla et al., 2016):

$$l^\mu \leftrightarrow o^A o^{\dot{B}}, \quad n^\mu \leftrightarrow \iota^A \iota^{\dot{B}}, \quad m^\mu \leftrightarrow o^A \iota^{\dot{B}}, \quad \bar{m}^\mu \leftrightarrow \iota^A o^{\dot{B}}; \quad (2)$$

hence for the type D the Lanczos spinor (López-Bonilla et al., 2015; Morales et al., 2016) is given by:

$$L_{ABCD} = \psi_2^{-\frac{2}{3}} (o_A o_B \iota_C + (o_A * \iota_B) o_C) (-\mu o_D + \pi \iota_D). \quad (3)$$

Similarly (Ares de Parga, Chavoya, & López-Bonilla, 1989):

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$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_0 &= \frac{q}{2}\kappa, & \Omega_3 &= -\frac{q}{2}\lambda, & \Omega_4 &= \frac{q}{2}\sigma, & \Omega_7 &= -\frac{q}{2}\nu, \\ & & \Omega_1 &= \frac{q}{6}\rho, & \Omega_2 &= -\frac{q}{6}\pi, & \Omega_5 &= \frac{q}{6}\tau, & \Omega_6 &= -\frac{q}{6}\mu, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

for the types N ($q = 1$) and III ($q = 2$), in the corresponding canonical tetrad, with the Lanczos spinor (Iturri-Hinojosa et al., 2017):

$$L_{ABC\dot{D}} = \iota_A \iota_B \iota_C (\Omega_0 \iota_{\dot{D}} - \Omega_4 o_{\dot{D}}) + (\iota_A \iota_B o_C + (o_A * \iota_B) \iota_C) (-\Omega_1 \iota_{\dot{D}} + \Omega_5 o_{\dot{D}}) + (o_A o_B \iota_C + (o_A * \iota_B) o_C) (\Omega_2 \iota_{\dot{D}} - \Omega_6 o_{\dot{D}}) + o_A o_B o_C (-\Omega_3 \iota_{\dot{D}} + \Omega_7 o_{\dot{D}}). \quad (5)$$

For the type O we may employ $q = 1$ or $q = 2$.

On the other hand, Andersson & Edgar (2001a; 2001b) proved that any Lanczos spinor can be generated via the relation (López-Bonilla et al., 2019):

$$L_{ABC\dot{D}} = \nabla^E_{\dot{D}} T_{ABCE}, T_{ABCE} = T_{(ABC)E}; \quad (6)$$

in Sec. 2 we construct T_{ABCE} for the cases (1) and (4).

Andersson-Edgar's potential

In (6) we use the expansion:

$$T_{ABCE} = \iota_A \iota_B \iota_C (\Lambda_0 \iota_E - \Lambda_4 o_E) + (\iota_A \iota_B o_C + (o_A * \iota_B) \iota_C) (-\Lambda_1 \iota_E + \Lambda_5 o_E) + (o_A o_B \iota_C + (o_A * \iota_B) o_C) (\Lambda_2 \iota_E - \Lambda_6 o_E) + o_A o_B o_C (-\Lambda_3 \iota_E + \Lambda_7 o_E), \quad (7)$$

to obtain the set of NP equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_0 &= \bar{\delta}\Lambda_0 - D\Lambda_4 + (\pi - 4\alpha)\Lambda_0 + 3\rho\Lambda_1 + (2\varepsilon + \rho)\Lambda_4 - 3\kappa\Lambda_5, \\ \Omega_1 &= \bar{\delta}\Lambda_1 - D\Lambda_5 - \lambda\Lambda_0 + (\pi - 2\alpha)\Lambda_1 + 2\rho\Lambda_2 + \pi\Lambda_4 + \rho\Lambda_5 - 2\kappa\Lambda_6, \\ \Omega_2 &= \bar{\delta}\Lambda_2 - D\Lambda_6 - 2\lambda\Lambda_1 + \pi\Lambda_2 + \rho\Lambda_3 + 2\pi\Lambda_5 + (\rho - 2\varepsilon)\Lambda_6 - \kappa\Lambda_7, \\ \Omega_3 &= \bar{\delta}\Lambda_3 - D\Lambda_7 - 3\lambda\Lambda_2 + (2\alpha + \pi)\Lambda_3 + 3\pi\Lambda_6 + (\rho - 4\varepsilon)\Lambda_7, \\ \Omega_4 &= \Delta\Lambda_0 - \delta\Lambda_4 + (\mu - 4\gamma)\Lambda_0 + 3\tau\Lambda_1 + (2\beta + \tau)\Lambda_4 - 3\sigma\Lambda_5, \\ \Omega_5 &= \Delta\Lambda_1 - \delta\Lambda_5 - \nu\Lambda_0 + (\mu - 2\gamma)\Lambda_1 + 2\tau\Lambda_2 + \mu\Lambda_4 + \tau\Lambda_5 - 2\sigma\Lambda_6, \\ \Omega_6 &= \Delta\Lambda_2 - \delta\Lambda_6 - 2\nu\Lambda_1 + \mu\Lambda_2 + \tau\Lambda_3 + 2\mu\Lambda_5 + (\tau - 2\beta)\Lambda_6 - \sigma\Lambda_7, \\ \Omega_7 &= \Delta\Lambda_3 - \delta\Lambda_7 - 3\nu\Lambda_2 + (2\gamma + \mu)\Lambda_3 + 3\mu\Lambda_6 + (\tau - 4\beta)\Lambda_7, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

hence (8) implies (4) for $\Lambda_2 = -\Lambda_5 = \frac{q}{6}$, $\Lambda_r = 0$, $r \neq 2, 5$, that is:

$$T_{ABCE} = \frac{q}{6} [(o_A o_B \iota_C + (o_A * \iota_B) o_C) \iota_E - (\iota_A \iota_B o_C + (o_A * \iota_B) \iota_C) o_E], \quad (9)$$

is a generator of the Lanczos spinor for arbitrary metrics with Petrov types O, N, and III, in the canonical null tetrad.

Let's remember that for type D vacuum spacetimes (Stephani et al., 2003; Lam-Estrada et al., 2015a):

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa = \sigma = \lambda = \nu = 0, & & \psi_2 \neq 0, & & \psi_r = 0, & r \neq 2, \\ D\psi_2 = 3\rho\psi_2, & & \Delta\psi_2 = -3\mu\psi_2, & & \delta\psi_2 = 3\tau\psi_2, & & \bar{\delta}\psi_2 = -3\pi\psi_2, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

then (1) is consequence from (8) for the values $\Lambda_2 = -\frac{3}{2}\Lambda_5 = \frac{3}{5}\psi_2^{-2/3}$, therefore:

$$T_{ABCE} = \frac{1}{5} \psi_2^{-2/3} [3(o_A o_B \iota_C + (o_A * \iota_B) o_C) \iota_E - 2(\iota_A \iota_B o_C + (o_A * \iota_B) \iota_C) o_E], \quad (11)$$

is a potential for the Lanczos spinor (3).

The construction of L_{ABCD} for arbitrary 4-spaces with Petrov types I, II, and D, is an open problem, and we consider that the relations (8) are important in such research.

Tensorial version of (6)

The tensorial version of the connection between the Lanczos spintensor and the Andersson-Edgar's potential means the existence of the tensors $F_{\mu\nu} = -F_{\nu\mu}$ and $U_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta}$ with the algebraic symmetries of the Weyl tensor, such that:

$$K_{\mu\nu\alpha} = U_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta}{}^{;\beta} + \frac{1}{3} (2F_{\mu\nu;\alpha} + F_{\alpha\nu;\mu} - F_{\alpha\mu;\nu} + F_{\nu\lambda}{}^{;\lambda} g_{\alpha\mu} - F_{\mu\lambda}{}^{;\lambda} g_{\alpha\nu}), \quad (12)$$

thus, the Lanczos potential has the properties (Lanczos, 1962b; Zund, 1973; Ahsan, 2019):

$$K_{abc} = -K_{bac}, \quad K_{abc} + K_{bca} + K_{cab} = 0, \quad K_a{}^b{}_b = 0, \quad (13)$$

and it generates the conformal tensor via the relation:

$$C_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} = K_{\mu\nu\alpha;\beta} - K_{\mu\nu\beta;\alpha} + K_{\alpha\beta\mu;\nu} - K_{\alpha\beta\nu;\mu} + \frac{1}{2} [(K_{\mu\beta} + K_{\beta\mu}) g_{\nu\alpha} + (K_{\nu\alpha} + K_{\alpha\nu}) g_{\mu\beta} - (K_{\mu\alpha} + K_{\alpha\mu}) g_{\nu\beta} - (K_{\nu\beta} + K_{\beta\nu}) g_{\mu\alpha}], K_{\mu\nu} \equiv K_{\mu\sigma\nu}{}^{;\sigma}. \quad (14)$$

We shall consider two applications of (12):

a). $U_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} = 0$. Then the Lanczos potential acquires the structure:

$$K_{\mu\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{3} (2F_{\mu\nu;\alpha} + F_{\alpha\nu;\mu} - F_{\alpha\mu;\nu} + F_{\nu\lambda}{}^{;\lambda} g_{\alpha\mu} - F_{\mu\lambda}{}^{;\lambda} g_{\alpha\nu}), \quad (15)$$

whose application in the Weyl-Lanczos equations (O'Donnell, 2003; Lam-Estrada et al., 2015b; Baykal, & Ünal, 2018), for arbitrary $F_{\mu\nu}$ gives $\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0}$ for any conformally flat space, that is, (15) is a Lanczos generator for arbitrary spacetimes of Petrov type O. If now we select the expression:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \frac{q}{2} (n_\mu l_\nu - n_\nu l_\mu), \quad (16)$$

then (15) is a Lanczos potential for arbitrary metrics types N and III, in the canonical null tetrad (Stephani et al. 2003; Newman & Penrose, 2009; López-Bonilla et al., 2016), for $q = 1$ and $q = 2$, respectively (Lam-Estrada et al., 2015a; López-Bonilla, & López-Vázquez, 2019a; 2019b; 2019c), reproducing the results obtained in Ares de Parga, Chavoya, & López-Bonilla, (1989).

b). $F_{\mu\nu} = 0$. Hence from (12):

$$K_{\mu\nu\alpha} = U_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta}{}^{;\beta}, \quad (17)$$

which is important in the Gödel cosmological model (Stephani et al., 2003; Gödel, 2000; Chandrasekhar, & Wright, 1961; Synge, 1976; López-Bonilla, Ovando, & Rivera-Rebolledo, 1997; Ahsan, López-Bonilla, & Rangel-Merino, 2009; Thapa et al., 2015):

$$ds^2 = (dx^0)^2 + 2 e^{x^3} dx^0 dx^1 + \frac{1}{2} e^{2x^3} (dx^1)^2 - (dx^2)^2 - (dx^3)^2, \quad (18)$$

because in López-Bonilla, López-Vázquez, & Vidal-Beltrán, (2019) was constructed the Lanczos generator $K_{\mu\nu\alpha} = -\frac{2}{9} C_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta}{}^{i\beta}$ with the structure (17).

We think that (12) with $U_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} \neq 0$ and $F_{\mu\nu} \neq 0$ will be useful in the search of Lanczos potentials for arbitrary spacetimes of Petrov types I, II and D (Acevedo, Enciso-Aguilar, & Lopez-Bonilla, 2006). In general relativity, the possible physical meaning of $K_{\mu\nu\alpha}$, is an open problem (Roberts, 1988; Cartin, 2003; Vishwakarma, 2020; Roberts, 2008; Riegert, 2023).

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